

OXIDATION OF PHENOLS BY MEANS OF HYDROGEN PEROXIDE IN PRESENCE OF INORGANIC CATALYSTS.

By B. C. KAR.

The oxidation of phenols by means of oxygen and hydrogen peroxide has been carried out by many investigators in presence of oxidases, peroxidases and inorganic catalysts. Recently hydroquinone has been oxidised to quinhydrone in presence of peroxidase obtained from common Indian vegetables—"Jhinga" (*Luffa acutangula*) and "Chow chow" (*Sechium edule*) by Dey and Sitharmanan (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 479; 1932, 9, 499). It has also been oxidised by peroxidase obtained from the fruits of "Linn" (*Tribulus terrestris*) by Ghatak and Giri (*Bull. Acad. Sci. U. P.*, 1933, 2, x63). Jules Wolff (*Compt. rend.*, 1908, 146, 781, 1217; 147, 747) has shown the similarity in behaviour of certain iron salts and peroxidases by oxidising hydroquinone and pyrogallol in presence of hydrogen peroxide. When a colloidal ferrous ferrocyanide solution containing 10 mg. of iron per litre is added to a saturated solution of quinol, quinhydrone is formed in a minute or two. This artificial peroxidase resembles the natural peroxidases in certain respects. Its activity is destroyed by excess of hydrogen peroxide like the natural enzymes. It loses its activity on boiling. It can be filtered through paper without alteration but it becomes inactive when filtered through collodion. Similar oxidations by means of atmospheric oxygen and hydrogen peroxide in presence of different metallic salts such as manganese, copper, uranium have been carried out. The author has undertaken this work with the object of studying the analogy of the colloidal catalysts of tungstic acid, molybdic acid and vanadic acid with peroxidases and throwing some light on the mechanism of the enzymatic reactions. For this purpose, a representative selection of substances is taken and their behaviour towards the colloidal catalysts and peroxidases studied.

A. Oxidation of Hydroquinone by means of Hydrogen Peroxide in Presence of Tungstic Acid Sol.

The oxidation of hydroquinone by means of hydrogen peroxide occurs in a consecutive manner. At low concentrations of hydrogen peroxide and sol, quinhydrone is the main product of oxidation as is the case with peroxidases. But as the concentrations of sol and hydrogen peroxide are

increased, it is converted into carbon dioxide and maleic acid. The equations may be expressed as follows.

Kempf (*Ber.*, 1906, 39, 3715) has oxidised quinone and hydroquinone by means of silver peroxide, sodium persulphate and ammonium persulphate and obtained carbon dioxide and maleic acid as the main products of oxidation, and formic acid and carbon monoxide are also produced in traces. The identical products of oxidation from hydroquinone by persulphates, and tungstic acid sol and hydrogen peroxide also support the formation of per-acids.

Isolation of the Products of Reaction.

Quinhydrone.—Quinhydrone can be easily isolated from the reaction mixture by starting with high concentrations of hydroquinone and adding equivalent amount of hydrogen peroxide in small quantities at a time, allowing a few minutes to elapse before each addition and cooling the reaction mixture in ice. Hydroquinone (2.5 g.) was dissolved in 150 c.c. of redistilled water and filtered. 0.05 *M*-sodium tungstate (5c.c.) in the form of sol was added and then equivalent amount of hydrogen peroxide. After the addition of hydrogen peroxide was complete, the reaction mixture was cooled in ice. The precipitated quinhydrone was filtered off, washed with ice-cold water and dried in a vacuum desiccator over sulphuric acid for a period of 72 hours. By this means a very pure quinhydrone was obtained having a sharp melting point of 171°, yield 0.4g.

Maleic Acid.—Hydroquinone (2 g.) was dissolved in redistilled water (100 c.c.) and filtered. Merck's perhydrol (35 c.c.) and 0.05 *M*-sodium tungstate (100 c.c.) were then added. After a few minutes, the reaction began with the evolution of heat and carbon dioxide. The reaction mixture was then allowed to stand for about two weeks with occasional shaking. When the reaction was complete, the mixture having a slight yellow

colour, was shaken with animal charcoal and excess of hydrogen peroxide was completely decomposed. It was then filtered and the filtrate did not liberate any iodine from a solution of potassium iodide in sulphuric acid. It was found to be distinctly acidic; it easily reduced potassium permanganate and decolourised bromine water. After evaporating the solution to dryness in a vacuum desiccator over sulphuric acid, maleic acid was extracted with ether.

Attempts were made to isolate any other products such as formic acid, oxalic acid and tartaric acid but were not successful.

Carbon dioxide. The formation of carbon dioxide can be easily shown by the method already given in the oxidation of cystine.

Measurement of Kinetics.

A sample of hydroquinone of chemically pure grade was taken and dissolved in water. In all our experiments we used redistilled water. Merck's perhydrol was taken for preparing fresh solution of hydrogen peroxide. The sol was prepared by the usual method.

In measuring the activity of peroxidase by oxidising hydroquinone to quinhydrone, Dey and Sitharaman (*loc. cit.*) separated the precipitated quinhydrone formed in a definite interval of time by filtration through Allihn tube. The quinhydrone was then dissolved in a mixture of alcohol and hydrochloric acid (1: 1) and a solution of KI was added. The liberated iodine was then estimated by thiosulphate. A correction for the loss of quinhydrone was made by carrying out a blank with known amount of quinhydrone but without hydrogen peroxide under identical conditions.

The author has found that instead of isolating the quinhydrone formed from the reaction mixture, which involves a certain amount of unavoidable error, it can be estimated in the reaction mixture itself spectrophotometrically by means of a König-Marten spectrophotometer. The reaction mixture after preparation was introduced into a small cell. It was then kept in a thermostat at a temperature of $(30 \pm 0.1^\circ)$. After the reaction period (usually 45 minutes) the spectrophotometric reading was taken at a wavelength $525\mu\mu$ and $\log \tan \theta_1 / \tan \theta$ found out, where θ is the zero-reading usually 45° on the circular scale of the spectrophotometer and θ_1 is the reading after the time interval. The thickness of the solution was 8 mm. In this region of the spectrum, Beer's law is obeyed as shown, by Fig. 1, where the values of $\log \tan \theta_1 / \tan \theta$ plotted against concentration of quinhydrone give a straight line. Quinhydrone was prepared by adding hydrogen peroxide of moderate strength drop by drop in a mixture of sol and concentrated

hydroquinone and cooling the mixture in ice as described before. A standard solution was prepared by dissolving it in a minimum quantity of hot water and roughly adjusted to the p_H of the reaction mixtures. All the experiments were repeated and concordant results were obtained. The results are expressed in terms of velocity constant

$$K = \frac{\log \tan \theta_1 - \log \tan \theta}{d \cdot t.}$$

where d = the thickness of the solution expressed in mm., t = time in minutes, and are tabulated below.

TABLE I.

Quinhydrone (M)	...	0.0035	0.007	0.0105	0.014	0.0175
$\log \frac{\tan \theta_1}{\tan \theta}$...	0.1001	0.1985	0.2991	0.3931	0.5056

TABLE II.

Effect of varying the concentration of hydroquinone.

Temp. = 30°. $p_H = 3.2$. $H_2O_2 = 0.0238M$. Sodium tungstate = 0.001M.

H.Q. (M)	...	0.00875	0.0175	0.02625	0.035	0.0525	0.07
K	...	0.00019	0.00034	0.00053	0.00072	0.00109	0.0014

TABLE III.

Effect of varying the concentration of H_2O_2 .

Temp. = 30°. $p_H = 3.2$. H.Q. = 0.035M. Na-tungstate = 0.001M.

Conc. of H_2O_2 (M)	..	0.0238	0.0476	0.0714	0.0953	0.1191	0.1429
K	...	0.0002	0.00086	0.00094	0.001	0.00103	0.00103

TABLE IV.

Effect of varying the concentration of catalyst.

Temp. = 30°. $p_H = 3.2$. H.Q. = 0.035M. $H_2O_2 = 0.0159M$.

Conc. of Na_2WO_4 (M)	...	0.00025	0.0005	0.001	0.002
K	...	0.00019	0.00034	0.0007	0.00121

FIG. 1.

FIG. 2.

TABLE V.

Effect of varying the p_H .

Temp. = 30°. H.Q. = 0.035M. H₂O₂ = 0.0238M. Na-tungstate = 0.001M.

p_H ...	2.8	3.2	4.2	The reaction is very rapid, gradually increasing with p_H .
K ...	0.0006	0.00072	0.0013	

TABLE VI.

Temperature coefficient.

$p_H = 3.2$. H₂O₂ = 0.0238M. Na-tungstate = 0.001M.

Temp.	H.Q. = 0.035M		Temp.	H.Q. = 0.07M	
	20°	30°		20°	30°
K ...	0.00024	0.00072	K ...	0.00045	0.0014

TABLE VII.

*Effect of salts.*Temp. = 30°. $p_n = 3.2$. H.Q. = 0.035M. $H_2O_2 = 0.0238M$.

Salts.	Conc. in the reaction mixture.	Conc. of sodium tungstate.	K.
—	—	$10^{-3}M$	0.00072
HgCl ₂	$10^{-3}M$	"	0.00072
KCN	"	"	0.00072

In order to measure the kinetics of reaction (III), that is, oxidation of quinone into carbon dioxide and maleic acid, we used higher concentrations of sol and hydrogen peroxide. With high concentrations of sol and hydrogen peroxide the velocities of the reactions (I) and (II) become very rapid in comparison with the reaction (III).

We have always used hydrogen peroxide in excess and have measured the kinetics of the reaction by observing the pressure of carbon dioxide developed, as indicated by a mercury manometer, at any moment at constant volume. It is found that a very good unimolecular constant is obtained by applying the equation

$$K = \frac{1}{t_2 - t_1} \log \frac{P_\infty - P_{t_1}}{P_\infty - P_{t_2}}$$

where P_{t_1} is the pressure in cm. of mercury at any time t_1 (in minutes) and P_{t_2} is the pressure at time t_2 and P_∞ is the pressure that should theoretically develop in accordance with the equation given, P_∞ is obtained by means of the well known equation given in p. 298. An actual calculation how P_∞ is obtained is given in Table I (*vide infra*). P_∞ may also be obtained with excess of H_2O_2 by noting the difference of initial and final reading after 72 hours, of the mercury manometer at the same temperature. The theoretical and experimental values are almost equal if proper allowance is made of the decomposition of hydrogen peroxide after 72 hours, CO_2 being absorbed by caustic potash, and the change in the barometric pressure.

Owing to initial disturbance due to the first reactions, the velocity was measured from 8-10% to 50-55%.

The experiments were carried out in a constant volume type of respirometer (commonly called the Warburg type of manometer). The increase

of pressure due to the production of carbon dioxide was indicated by a manometer filled with mercury. The total volume upto the constant mercury level in the manometer was 45.2 c.c. and was determined by filling the vessel and the tube with mercury. The reaction mixture occupied 10 c.c. and the rest 35.2 c.c. was the amount of dead space. No carbon dioxide was formed by the action of hydrogen peroxide on hydroquinone in the absence of the sol. The whole system was shaken 60 to 65 times per minute throughout the experiment. The vessels were completely immersed in a big thermostat which was maintained at a temperature of $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$. To correct for the changes of temperature and the barometric pressure, a similar vessel which contained only water was used. It was always observed by keeping strict control in which the carbon dioxide was absorbed by caustic potash, in a suitable reservoir, that there was very slight spontaneous decomposition of hydrogen peroxide during the course of the experiment. All the experiments were repeated and reproducible results were obtained. In Table VIII is given the results of a typical experiment in detail.

TABLE VIII.

Temp. = 25° . $p_H = 1.26$. $H_2O_2 = 0.72M$. Na-tungstate = $0.01M$. H.Q. = $0.025M$. Composition of the mixture = 2 c.c. water + 2 c.c. H.Q. + 2 c.c. dilute HCl + 2 c.c. H_2O_2 + 2 c.c. sol.

Time.	Manometric readings.		Diff.	K.
	A.	B.		
0 min.	12	12	—	—
17	12	12.55	0.55 (1)	—
57	12	14.75	2.75 (2)	0.00122 (1&2)
94	12	16.6	4.6 (3)	0.00122 (1&3)
132.5	12	18.25	6.25 (4)	0.0012 (1&4)
169	12	19.7	7.7 (5)	0.0012 (1&5)
217.5	12	21.2	9.2 (6)	0.00116 (1&6)
P_∞	—	—	21.4	Mean 0.0012

Calculation of P_∞ .—The amount of CO_2 that should theoretically

generate in the above reaction mixture according to the equations given is 22 mg. and the volume it should occupy at N. T. P.

$$= \frac{22}{0.089 \times 22} \text{ c.c.} = 11.236 \text{ c.c.} = 11236 \text{ c. mm.},$$

0.089 mg. being the weight of 1 c.c. hydrogen at N. T. P. and 22 being the density of CO₂. Now the equation is

$$X = h \frac{V_0 \frac{273}{T} + V_l \alpha}{P_0}$$

where x = the amount of gas evolved in c. mm. at N.T.P. = 11236 c. mm.,

h = corresponding reading of the manometer = P_{∞} ?

V_0 = the volume of the gas space in the vessel = 35200 c.mm.

T = absolute temperature of the water-bath = $(273 + 25)^{\circ} = 298^{\circ}$

V_l = the volume of the liquid in the vessel = 10000 c. mm.

α = the solubility of CO₂ in the liquid of the vessel at N. T. P. = 0.759

(cf. Bohr, *Ann. phys. Chem.*, 1899, 68, 504).

P_0 = the normal pressure = 760 mm. Hg.

$$h = \frac{11236 \times 760 \text{ mm.}}{35200 \frac{273}{298} + 10000 \times 0.759} = 214 \text{ mm.} = 21.4 \text{ cm.}$$

TABLE IX.

Effect of varying the concentration of hydroquinone.

Temp. = 25°. $p_H = 1.26$. $H_2O_2 = 0.72M$. Na-tungstate = 0.01M.

H ₂ O ₂ (M) ...	0.0083	0.0125	0.0166	0.025	0.033
K (mean) ...	0.00125	0.00121	0.0012	0.0012	0.00118

* Here we have assumed the whole apparatus at temperature T . The manometric tube was, however, at room temperature. Since the room temperature was near about T and the volume of the manometer above the water level was very small, the error introduced may safely be neglected.

TABLE X.

*Effect of varying the concentration of hydrogen peroxide.*Temp. = 25°. $p_H = 1.26$. H.Q. = 0.025M. Na-tungstate = 0.01M.

H ₂ O ₂ (M)	...	0.18	0.36	0.54	0.72	1.08
K	...	0.00067	0.00088	0.00106	0.0012	0.0014

1/K plotted against 1/conc. of H₂O₂ gives approximately a straight line (cf. Fig. 2).

TABLE XI.

*Effect of varying the concentration of sodium tungstate.*Temp. = 25°. $p_H = 1.26$. H₂O₂ = 0.72M. H.Q. = 0.025M.

Na-tungstate (M)	...	0.005	0.01	0.015	0.02
K	...	0.00068	0.0012	0.00165	0.00204

TABLE XII.

*Effect of varying the p_H .*Temp. = 25°. H.Q. = 0.025M. H₂O₂ = 0.72M. Na-tungstate = 0.01M.

p_H	...	1.26	1.7	2.25	3.1	4.1	5.1
K	...	0.0012	0.00122	0.0012	0.00119	0.00118	0.00126

At p_H 5.1, we used acetate buffer at suitable concentration so that it did not cause any decomposition of hydrogen peroxide. It has got no influence of its own on the activity of the sol.

TABLE XIII.

Effect of varying the temperature. $p_H = 1.26$. H₂O₂ = 0.72M. Na-tungstate = 0.01M.

Temp.	Conc. of H.Q.	K.	Temp.	Conc. of H.Q.	K.
25°	0.0125M	0.00121	25°	0.025M	0.0012
35°	0.0125	0.00268	35°	„	0.0029

The temperature coefficient of the reaction is $Q_{10} = 2.4$ to 2.5.

TABLE XIV.

*Influence of potassium cyanide.*Temp. = 25°. $p_H = 4.1$. H.Q. = 0.025M. $H_2O_2 = 0.72M$.

Conc. of Na-tungstate.	Conc. of KCN.	K.
0.01M	...	0.0012
0.01	0.0025M	0.0012
0.01	0.005	0.00119

Potassium cyanide has got no influence on the catalytic activity of the sol.

B. Oxidation of Hydroquinone by means of Hydrogen Peroxide in Presence of Molybdic Acid Sol.

In the case of molybdic acid sol the experimental procedure is exactly the same as in the case of tungstic acid sol. The products of reaction are exactly the same with both the sols. The velocity of the oxidation of hydroquinone to quinone can be measured in exactly the same way as the tungstic acid sol. The results of kinetic measurements of the oxidation of quinone to CO_2 and maleic acid are given below. The velocity coefficient is determined in exactly the same way as the tungstic acid sol.

TABLE XV.

*Effect of varying the concentration of hydroquinone.*Temp. = 25°. $p_H = 1.12$. $H_2O_2 = 0.72M$. Am. molybdate = 0.02M.

H.Q. (M)	...	0.0083	0.0125	0.0166	0.025	0.033
K (mean)	...	0.00135	0.00131	0.0013	0.00132	0.00127

TABLE XVI.

*Effect of varying the concentration of H_2O_2 .*Temp. = 25°. $p_H = 2.5$. H.Q. = 0.025M. Am. molybdate = 0.005M.

H_2O_2 (M)	...	0.18	0.36	0.54	0.72	1.08
K	...	0.00114	0.00117	0.00119	0.00122	0.00128

The velocity constant is practically independent of the concentration of hydrogen peroxide.

TABLE XVII.

*Effect of varying the concentration of Am. molybdate.*Temp. = 25°. $p_H = 1.12$. H.Q. = 0.025M. $H_2O_2 = 0.72M$.

Am. molybdate (M) ...	0.01	0.015	0.02	0.025
K ...	0.00069	0.00099	0.0013	0.0016

TABLE XVIII.

*Effect of varying the p_H .*Temp. = 25°. H.Q. = 0.025M. $H_2O_2 = 0.72M$. Am. molybdate = 0.02M.

p_H ...	1.12	1.51	1.85	2.1	3.1	4.2	5.0
K ...	0.0013	0.00194	0.00225	0.00268	0.0030	0.00314	0.0032

The velocity constant increases as the p_H increases.

TABLE XIX.

Effect of varying the temperature. $p_H = 1.12$. $H_2O_2 = 0.72M$. Am. molybdate = 0.02M.

Temp.	Conc. of H.Q.	K.	Temp.	Conc. of H.Q.	K.
25°	0.025M	0.00133	25°	0.025M	0.0013
35	"	0.0027	35	"	0.00272

The temperature coefficient of the reaction is about 2. The reaction can similarly be carried out in presence of vanadic acid sol.

C. Oxidation of Pyrogallol by means of Hydrogen Peroxide in Presence of Tungstic Acid Sol.

The oxidation of pyrogallol in presence of peroxidase has been carried out by many workers. Prof. Willstätter and co-workers (*Annalen*, 1918, 416, 21; 1923, 430, 269; 1926, 449, 156, 175) have studied the preparation, purification and activity of peroxidases derived from different sources. They studied the peroxidase activity by oxidising pyrogallol and estimating the quantity of purpurogallin formed. Rice and Hanzawa (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1922, 14, 201) have investigated the peroxidase activity in milk by oxidising

pyrogallol in presence of hydrogen peroxide. Getchell and Walton (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1931, 91, 419) have studied the influence of some factors on the activity of peroxidase in the oxidation of pyrogallol to purpurogallin.

Many other similar works have been carried out for the determination of peroxidase activity by oxidising pyrogallol. Purpurogallin is obtained by the oxidation of pyrogallol in presence of low concentrations of tungstic acid sol and hydrogen peroxide. In this paper, experiments were carried out to compare the activity of tungstic acid sol with peroxidases using pyrogallol as substrate.

Isolation of Purpurogallin.

Pyrogallic acid (5 g.) was dissolved in 150 c. c. of redistilled water and filtered. 0.1 *M*-sodium tungstate (2 c. c.) in the form of sol was added. A dilute solution of hydrogen peroxide was then added in small quantities at a time. When the addition of hydrogen peroxide was complete, the reaction mixture was cooled in ice. Purpurogallin was separated, filtered, washed and then dried. It was then recrystallised from ether, yield 0.4 g.

A pure sample of pyrogallic acid was taken and dissolved in conductivity water. A fresh solution of pyrogallic acid was prepared daily. Merck's perhydrol was used for preparing fresh solution of hydrogen peroxide. The reaction was carried out at 30° in a Pyrex conical flask in which pyrogallol, hydrogen peroxide and sol were added, the total volume being made 50 c.c. Pyrogallol was oxidised to purpurogallin which could be easily extracted with ether.

In the case of oxidation with peroxidase, the reaction has been arrested after a period of ten to twelve minutes by the addition of suitable inhibitors such as strong hydrochloric acid, strong sulphuric acid, mercuric chloride and potassium cyanide. But in the case of sol as no such suitable inhibitor is available to stop the reaction, we had necessarily to prolong the time of measurement. One hour reaction period was found to be most suitable under the prevailing experimental conditions. Purpurogallin formed was twice extracted with ether in a separating funnel, first with 15 c.c. and then with 10 c.c. As the dye thus extracted was not absolutely pure but contained slight amount of colouring matter, the combined extract was washed with 10 c.c. of distilled water three or four times. By this means a very pure pigment was obtained. The volume of the extract was then made 20 c.c. and the value of $\log \tan \theta_1 / \tan \theta$ was obtained spectrophotometrically at wave-length 525 μ . The thickness of the solution used was 4 cm.

The previous workers have estimated the amount of purpurogallin formed, by comparing the extract colorimetrically with a standard. But the present author has found that a great saving of time and trouble can be effected by estimating it spectrophotometrically.

FIG. 3.

TABLE XX.

Purpurogallin (mg./litre).	Log $\frac{\tan \theta_1}{\tan \theta}$.
40	0.0536
80	0.1164
120	0.1655
160	0.2259
200	0.2875

Table XX gives the values of $\log \tan \theta_1 / \tan \theta$ for various concentrations of purpurogallin at wave-length 525μ , the thickness of the solution used being 4 cm. In this region of the spectrum Beer's law is obeyed as shown in Fig. 3, where the values of $\log \tan \theta_1 / \tan \theta$ plotted against concentration give a straight line. From the readings in the spectrophotometer for the above wave-length, it is obvious that the concentration of an unknown solution can conversely be calculated. Purpurogallin was prepared by the method of Perkin and Steven (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1903, 83, 192) and was recrystallised from alcohol and ether. The results are tabulated below.

TABLE XXI.

Effect of varying the concentration of pyrogallol.

Temp. = 30° . $p_n = 4.3$. $H_2O_2 = 8 \times 10^{-3} M$. Na-tungstate = $10^{-4} M$.

Pyrogallol (mg./c.c.)	...	0.5	1	2	3	
Purpurogallin (mg./litre)	...	0.71	105	160	200	228

TABLE XXII.

*Effect of varying the concentration of H₂O₂.*Temp. = 30°. $p_n = 4.3$. Na-tungstate = $10^{-4}M$. Pyrogallol = 1 mg./c.c.

H ₂ O ₂ (M) ...	2×10^{-3}	4×10^{-3}	8×10^{-3}	1.2×10^{-2}	1.6×10^{-2}	2×10^{-2}
Purpurogallin (mg./litre) ...	77	88	105	124	135	135

TABLE XXIII.

*Effect of varying the concentration of catalyst.*Temp. = 30°. $p_n = 3.1$. H₂O₂ = $4 \times 10^{-3}M$. Pyrogallol = 1 mg./c.c.

Na-tungstate ...	5×10^{-5}	10^{-4}	2×10^{-4}	3×10^{-4}
Purpurogallin (mg./litre) ...	33	66	124	180

TABLE XXIV.

*Effect of varying the p_n .*Temp. = 30°. H₂O₂ = $4 \times 10^{-3}M$. Na-tungstate = $10^{-4}M$.
Pyrogallol = 1 mg./c.c.

p_n ...	2.8	3.1	3.5	4.3	5.3	6.3
Purpurogallin (mg./litre) ...	54	65	77	88	147	100

TABLE XXV.

TABLE XXVI.

Temperature coefficient.

H ₂ O ₂ = $4 \times 10^{-3}M$. Na-tungstate = $10^{-4}M$. $p_n = 4.3$.				Pyrogallol = 4 mg./c.c. H ₂ O ₂ = $4 \times 10^{-3}M$. Na-tungstate = $2 \times 10^{-4}M$. $p_n = 4.2$.			
	Pyrogallol = 1 mg./c.c.		Pyrogallol = 4 mg./c.c.				
Temp.	20°	30°	20°	30°	Temp.	10°	20°
Purpurogallin (mg./litre)	27	88	50	150	Purpurogallin (mg./litre)	44	106

TABLE XXVII.

*Effect of salts.*Temp. = 30°. $H_2O_2 = 4 \times 10^{-3} M$. $p_H = 3.1$. Pyrogallol = 1 mg./c.c.

Salt.	Conc. in the reaction mixture.	Na tungstate.	Purpurogallin (mg./litre).
—	—	$10^{-4} M$	66
HgCl ₂	$10^{-3} M$	10^{-4}	66
KCN	10^{-4}	„	66

Oxidation of pyrogallol can similarly be carried out in presence of molybdic and vanadic acids.

D. Oxidation of Guaiacol by means of Hydrogen Peroxide in Presence of Tungstic Acid Sol.

The oxidation of *ortho*-cresol and guaiacol has been extensively carried out in presence of oxidases, peroxidases and other metallic salts (Bertrand, *Compt. rend.*, 1903, 137, 1269; Bansi and Ucko, *Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1926, 157, 192; 1927, 165, 52; 169, 177).

According to Bertrand, guaiacol is oxidised in presence of laccase to a red compound tetraguaiacoquinone according to the following equation,

Peroxidase acts as laccase in presence of hydrogen peroxide.

Tetraguaiacoquinone is a fine crystalline powder having a purplish-red colour with a faint green metallic lustre. It is insoluble in water, slightly soluble in ether and a little less so in alcohol, still less so in benzene and readily soluble in chloroform giving a red colour. It is also soluble in alkalis forming coloured solutions.

With low concentrations of tungstic acid sol and hydrogen peroxide, the oxidation of guaiacol proceeds similarly and the product of oxidation can be easily extracted with chloroform.

The oxidation of guaiacol was carried out in exactly the same manner as the oxidation of pyrogallol and hydroquinone, at 25° . The solution of guaiacol was prepared in redistilled water. The reaction was carried out in Pyrex conical flask in which guaiacol, hydrogen peroxide and sol were added, the total volume being made 25 c.c. After the required time interval, the entire mixture was extracted with 25 c.c. of chloroform, leaving the reaction mixture colourless. The red chloroformic solution was then washed with water. The volume was made upto 25 c.c. and $\log \tan \theta_1 / \tan \theta$ determined. With the progress of the reaction, the depth of the colour of the chloroformic solution increased which was followed by the rotation of the angle in the König-Martens spectrophotometer. All measurements were made at wave-length $525 \mu\mu$ in a glass cell, the thickness of the solution being 1 cm. The experiments were all repeated and reproducible results were obtained. The results of kinetic measurements are represented graphically by plotting $\log \tan \theta_1 / \tan \theta$ against time. Table XXVIII gives the results of a typical experiment in detail.

Fig. 4.

Effect of varying the conc. of reducing substrate.

Conc. of $H_2O_2 = 0.036M$.
Na-tungstate = $0.002M$. $\rho_n = 4.4$. $t = 24^{\circ}$.

Fig 5.

Influence of hydrogen peroxide.

Guaiacol = $0.0198M$.
Na-tungstate = $0.002M$.
 $\rho_n = 4.4$. Temp. = 25° .

Fig. 6.

Influence of hydrogen number.

Guaiacol = 0.0198M. $H_2O_2 = 0.012M$. Na-tungstate = 0.002M.
Temp. = 25°.

TABLE XXVIII.

Temp. = 25°. $p_H = 4.4$ $H_2O_2 = 0.036M$. Na-tungstate = 0.002M.
Guaiacol = 0.0588 M. Composition of the reaction mixture = 20 c.c. guaiacol soln. + 1 c.c. water + 2 c.c. sol + 2 c.c. H_2O_2 .

Time	...	0	5	10	15	20	25	30
Spectrophotometric readings	...	46	47.5	51.5	56.5	61	65	68.5
Log tan $\theta_1 / \text{tan } \theta$...	—	0.02279	0.08423	0.16406	0.24109	0.31617	0.38944

Effect of varying the temperature.

Guaiacol = 0.0396M. H_2O_2 = 0.36M.
Na-tungstate = 0.02M. $p_H = 4.4$.

Guaiacol = 0.0294M. H_2O_2 = 0.36M.
Na-tungstate = 0.02M. $p_H = 4.4$.

Fig. 7a.

Fig. 7b.

The reaction can similarly be carried out in presence of molybdic acid sol and vanadic acid sol.

E. Oxidation of α -Naphthol and p-Phenylenediamine Mixture by Hydrogen Peroxide in Presence of Tungstic Acid Sol.

A mixture of α -naphthol and *p*-phenylenediamine or the so-called Nadi reagent has been extensively oxidised to measure the activities of oxidases, peroxidases, and other heavy metals as iron and copper (Guthrie, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 53, 242; Harrison, *Biochem. J.*, 1929, 23, 982; Wertheimer, *Fermentforsch.*, 1926, 8, 497).

p-Phenylenediamine on oxidation gives the corresponding dark purple di-imino compound

while in the case of Nadi reagent containing an equimolecular mixture of dimethyl-*p*-phenylenediamine and α -naphthol, the reaction consists in the oxidation of the diamine compound to a nitroso compound and the condensation of the latter with α -naphthol forming indophenol blue.

The same end-products were obtained by replacing the oxidases or the peroxidases with tungstic acid sol.

A solution of *p*-phenylenediamine (0.1%) and a solution of α -naphthol of same strength were prepared fresh every day and filtered. The reaction was carried out in a Pyrex conical flask in which the reactants and the sol were added in suitable concentrations, the total volume being made 25 c.c. The flask was then immersed in a thermostat at 30°. At timed intervals the entire mixture was extracted with 25 c.c. of toluene leaving the reaction mixture colourless. No appreciable amount of spontaneous oxidation took place in presence of hydrogen peroxide alone at these intervals. The total volume was then made up to 25 c.c. and the spectrophotometric reading taken at wave-length 525 $\mu\mu$, the thickness of the solution used being 0.5 cm. It has been found that the velocity coefficient of the reaction can be determined approximately by means of the equation

$$K = \frac{\log \tan \theta_2 - \log \tan \theta_1}{d(t_2 - t_1)}$$

where θ_2 is the spectrophotometric reading corresponding to the time t_2 and θ_1 corresponding to the time t_1 , d being the thickness of the solution in mm. Indophenol in toluene solution has been found to obey the Beer's law at wave-length $525 \mu\mu$. The results are tabulated below.

TABLE XXIX.

Effect of varying the concentration of reducing substrate.

$H_2O_2 = 0.02M$. Na -tungstate $= 0.002M$. $p_u = 5$. Temp. $= 30^\circ$.

<i>p</i> -Phenylenediamine in c.c. (0.1% solution filtered) ...	2	4	6	8
α -Naphthol in c.c. (0.1% solution filtered) ...	2	4	6	8
K (mean) ...	0.0015	0.003	0.0046	0.0064

TABLE XXX.

Effect of varying the concentration of hydrogen peroxide.

Na -tungstate $= 0.002M$. $p_u = 5$. Temp. $= 30^\circ$. *p*-Phenylenediamine $= 4$ c.c. α -Naphthol $= 4$ c.c.

$H_2O_2(M)$...	0.005	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.05
K ...	0.0028	0.0029	0.003	0.00315	0.0032

*F. Oxidation of Catechol, *p*-Cresol, and other Phenols by means of Hydrogen Peroxide in Presence of Tungstic Acid Sol.*

Catechol, phenol, *m*- and *p*-cresol have been oxidised by tyrosinase and peroxidase with the formation of *ortho*-quinone by Pugh and Raper (*Biochem. J.*, 1927, 21, 1370). *o*-Quinones are very unstable substances and have been isolated as dianilinoquinones by carrying out the reactions in presence of aniline. The reactions with catechol have been represented as follows :

But quite recently it has been suggested by Wagreich and Nelson (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1936, 118, 459) that in the oxidation of catechol by tyrosinase, it is not *o*-quinone but a hydroxy derivative of it which reacts with aniline forming dianilinoquinone according to the equation

*Dianilino-*o*-benzoquinone* as described above can also be isolated by the oxidation of catechol in presence of tungstic acid sol and hydrogen peroxide by the method of Pugh and Raper as given below.

Catechol (25 g.) and aniline (5 c.c.) were dissolved in a litre of water. Hydrogen peroxide (20 c.c., 5%) and 0.05*M*-sodium tungstate (10 c.c.) in the form of sol were added. After some time a red precipitate was obtained which after 3 days, was filtered off, washed with 1% hydrochloric acid to remove excess of aniline and then with water. It was dried *in vacuo* and extracted in a Soxhlet apparatus with acetone. On evaporation of the acetone solution, bright red needles separated out. It was further purified by recrystallisation from acetone, m.p. 191°, yield, 1 g.; other properties were identical with those of the product obtained by Pugh and Raper (*loc. cit.*).

Dianilino-homoquinone-anil (C₂₃H₂₁ON₃) can similarly be isolated from *p*-cresol, but the yield of pure product is small, some tarry substance also being produced. Attempts were made to isolate similar anilino-compound from tyrosine but were not successful. This is probably due to the fact that the *o*-quinone derived from tyrosine undergoes further reaction, *i.e.*, form indole derivative (Raper, *Biochem. J.*, 1927, 21, 89).

From the above, it is evident that *o*-quinones are produced by the action of tungstic acid sol and hydrogen peroxide on *p*-cresol and catechol.

All phenolic substances can be oxidised by means of hydrogen peroxide in presence of sodium tungstate or tungstic acid sol, ammonium molybdate or molybdic acid sol and vanadic acid, finally with the production of carbon dioxide.

Tincture of guaiacum has been extensively used in the detection of peroxidases. In presence of peroxidases and hydrogen peroxide it turns blue. Replacing the peroxidases by sols, the same blueing of guaiacum takes place.

G. Oxidation of Tyrosine and Tryptophan by means of Hydrogen Peroxide in Presence of Tungstic Acid Sol.

The oxidation of tyrosine and tryptophan which are substances of metabolic interest and are widely distributed in animal and plant organisms, have been carried out by many workers in presence of tyrosinase and peroxidase with the formation of coloured products. The problem of finding out the mechanism of oxidation of tyrosine by tyrosinase is a long-standing one and the exact nature of tyrosinase whether it consists of a single enzyme or a mixture of different enzymes has not yet been elucidated. All attempts to separate tyrosinase into components have hitherto failed.

Various theories have been put forward from time to time to explain the course of oxidation of tyrosine by tyrosinase. Bach (*Biochem. Z.*, 1914, 60, 221) suggested that the initial action of tyrosinase on tyrosine could be represented as

Folpners (*Biochem. Z.*, 1916, 78, 180) showed that the first action of tyrosinase on tyrosine was the production of ammonia and a hydroxyaldehyde by the action of a deamidase according to the equation

The second ferment causes a further oxidation of the aldehyde (or its condensation product with ammonia) to a black pigment melanin. In the case of phenylglycine, the author succeeded in actually demonstrating the presence of a deamidase in that he isolated benzaldehyde in the form of its

from tyrosine only in this respect that it does not contain any phenolic hydroxyl group, is not attacked by tyrosinase. Similar is the case with tungstic acid and molybdic acid sols. They attack all monohydric and dihydric phenols with the formation of coloured products but not phenylalanine. Though *o*-dihydroxy derivative is produced by the action of tyrosinase on tyrosine (Raper, *Biochem. J.*, 1926, 20, 735) which is then converted into *p*-quinone, the *o*-quinone can not be isolated as aniline compound as can be done with other phenols (Pugh and Raper, *Biochem. J.*, 1927, 21, 1370). This is due to further reaction, *i.e.*, the formation of indole derivative from tyrosine. Similar is the case when the tyrosinase is replaced by sol and hydrogen peroxide. No aniline compound could be isolated. It has been shown by Happold and Raper (*Biochem. J.*, 1925, 19, 92) and Robinson and McCance (*ibid.*, 1925, 19, 251) that the system phenol-tyrosinase can bring about the deamination of an amino-acid added to the system. This has been explained by Happold and Raper to be due to the formation of an *ortho*-quinone which attacks the amino-acids. But it has been shown by Robinson and McCance (*loc. cit.*) that tyrosine is unable to bring about the external oxidation of amino-acids as *p*-cresol and other phenols do. The author in a subsequent paper (to be published shortly) has shown that in the above system tyrosinase can be replaced by sol-hydrogen peroxide with the same results but no deamination takes place when tyrosine is used instead of *p*-cresol. Melanin, a black pigment, has been isolated as the end-product in the oxidation of tyrosine by tyrosinase. At low concentrations of sol and hydrogen peroxide a black pigment containing 10-15% inorganic matter as impurities has been isolated from tyrosine. But when the concentrations of sol and hydrogen peroxide are increased, both tyrosine and tryptophan are oxidised with the production of carbon dioxide, ammonia and other products, the nature of which is in the course of investigation.

From the above, it is clear that there is a similarity in the behaviour of tyrosinase and sol-hydrogen peroxide towards tyrosine but with high concentration of hydrogen peroxide ammonia is produced. So experiments were carried out to show whether this deamination of tyrosine takes place during the first stages of the reaction as supposed by Bach, Folpmers and others in the case of tyrosinase. The results were found to be entirely negative. The black pigment that has been isolated is found to be free from any ammonia. When treated with sol-hydrogen peroxide it gives ammonia and carbon dioxide showing that ammonia is not the initial product of reaction. Further investigations to determine the course of the reaction are in progress.

Ammonia.—Ammonia was determined at various stages of the reaction by the method of Whitehorn (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1923, **86**, 751). Tyrosine (Pfansteihl, 0.2 g.) was dissolved in a minimum quantity of hydrochloric acid and the volume made up to 100 c.c. The solution was then brought to a p_{H} 4 to 5. Hydrogen peroxide (5 c.c., 3 molecules of hydrogen peroxide for each molecule of tyrosine) and 10 c.c. of sol (6 c.c., 0.05M- Na_2WO_4) were added and the ammonia was determined by the above method. The process consists in filtering the solution through a layer of permutite. About 5 c.c. of finely granular permutite were placed in uniform layer in the funnel of a Witt's apparatus connected with a water-pump. The permutite layer was then washed with 2% acetic acid to neutralise any alkali present and then several times with distilled water to remove the traces of acetic acid. When the reaction mixture containing ammonia was filtered, it was washed with 15 to 20 c.c. of distilled water four to five times. The permutite containing ammonia was then removed to a test tube and 8 c.c. of a 10% solution of sodium hydroxide added and shaken for a minute. It was then filtered and in the filtrate ammonia was estimated by modified Nessler's solution (Bock and Benedict formula). In the above reaction mixture no ammonia could be detected at any stage. Test estimations in which 0.5 to 1 mg. of ammonia was initially added, showed that the added amounts could be estimated almost quantitatively. But when excess of hydrogen peroxide (4 c.c., Merck's perhydrol) was added in the above mixture, the presence of ammonia could be easily detected after 24 hours.

Isolation of the Black Pigment.—Tyrosine (1 g.) was dissolved in minimum quantity of strong HCl and the volume made up to 100 c.c. Hydrogen peroxide (10 c.c., 5 molecules of hydrogen peroxide for every molecule of tyrosine) and 15 c.c. of sol (10 c.c., 0.05 M- Na_2WO_4) were added. After standing for two to three days a deposit of black pigment was obtained at the bottom of the solution. The supernatant clear solution was removed as far as practicable without disturbing the precipitate. It was then purified by boiling with successive quantities of dilute hydrochloric acid and finally washed with hot water by decantation for 15 to 20 times. After filtration it was washed again and dried in a vacuum desiccator containing sulphuric acid. On analysis it was found to contain 10 to 15% ash and nitrogen was present in sufficient quantity as shown by qualitative test.

In presence of milk peroxidase and H_2O_2 both tyrosine and tryptophan are oxidised (Elliot, *Biochem. J.*, 1932, **26**, 10) while in presence of plant peroxidase only tyrosine is oxidised and tryptophan is not (*Biochem. J.* 1932, **26**, 1281). With tungstic acid and molybdic acid sols both tyrosine and tryptophan are oxidised, the former more easily than the latter.

The velocity of the first partial process of the above reaction has been studied by Raper and Wornall (*Biochem. J.*, 1923, 17, 454) and has been found to be of monomolecular type. The velocity coefficients are approximately constant throughout the reaction.

D I S C U S S I O N.

Below is given a comparison of the results obtained by the oxidation of phenolic substances in presence of peroxidase and tungstic acid sol by means of hydrogen peroxide.

(1) At low concentration of hydrogen peroxide, the products of reaction are same in both cases.

(2) In the case of peroxidase, as the concentration of reducing substrate is increased, the amount of the product of reaction increases upto a certain value depending on the experimental conditions and then begins to decrease (*cf.* Getchell and Walton, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1931, 91, 419; Dey and Sitharaman, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 499). But in the case of tungstic acid sol as the concentration of the oxidisable substances increases, the amount of the product of reaction increases but the relation is not linear.

(3) In the plant peroxidase reactions, the activity of the peroxidase increases with increase in the concentration of hydrogen peroxide but excess of hydrogen peroxide retards the activity and in large quantities destroys it altogether (*Ber.*, 1904, 37, 3787; *Annalen*, 1926, 449, 175). But peroxidasic action of oxyhæmoglobin, contrary to that of plant peroxidase, increases pronouncedly with rising H_2O_2 concentration and is different in different kinds of animals. With tungstic acid sol, the activity of the sol slowly increases upto a certain value and further increase of hydrogen peroxide has very little influence.

(4) The increase in the concentration of both peroxidase and sol influences the reaction velocity but not in strict proportion to their increase in concentration.

(5) With pyrogallol substrate and horse-radish peroxidase the optimum p_H has been given as 7 by Bansi and Ucko (*Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1926, 159, 235). With hydroquinone substrate and "Chow chow" peroxidase, the optimum p_H lies between 4.8 and 5.2 (Dey and Sitharaman, *loc. cit.*). The optimum p_H for the oxidation of guaiacol is between p_H 5 and 5.2 (Bansi and Ucko, *loc. cit.*). But with sol and pyrogallol the optimum p_H is 5.3 and with guaiacol the optimum p_H is 3.5.

(6) In the twelve minutes' reaction period, the weight of purpurogalin formed at 10° is 140% of that formed at 0° , and at 20° , 120%

of that formed at 10°. From this, the temperature coefficient is given to be 1.4 in the 0-10° range, and 1.2 in the 10-20° range by Getchell and Walton (*loc. cit.*) The temperature coefficient in the case of sol and pyrogallol is 2.4 in the 10-20° range and 3.1 in the 20-30° range.

(7) Potassium cyanide and mercuric chloride are strong poisons to peroxidases but they have got practically no influence upon the sol.

(8) Most of the peroxidases are heat-labile except the pseudo-peroxidases which are thermostable. The sol is heat-stable and in this respect it resembles the pseudo-peroxidases.

(9) Ultraviolet light is very active in destroying the activity of the peroxidase (*Biochem. Z.* 1931, 241, 384; *Compt. rend.*, 1911, 183, 979). But in the case of the sol the reverse case is found. Many photochemical reactions are being carried out in our laboratory in presence of the sol.

The mechanism of the oxidation of phenols by hydrogen peroxide in presence of tungstic acid, molybdic acid and vanadic acid sols can be explained by the per-acid formation theory as has been done in the case of sulphhydryl compounds.

But Fernandes (*Atti. R. Acad. Lincei*, 1925, 1, 439; *Gazzetta*, 1925, 55, 424) has shown that organic compounds containing two hydroxyl groups in the *ortho* position react to give complex derivatives with salts of molybdic, tungstic and uranic acids. He has isolated two series of compounds according to the conditions and proportions of substances employed. The two series are

where X = Mo, W, or U; R = H, K, Na, Tl, guanidine, or pyridine; Z = C₆H₄O₂ or C₆H₄O₃.

Compounds of neither type are formed by either di- or trihydroxylated compounds unless at least two hydroxyl groups occupy *ortho* position to one another, such relationship being necessary for the development of co-ordination valency.

The author also has prepared similar complexes of pyrocatechol and pyrogallol with salts of tungstic acid and molybdic acid, and has studied their reactions with hydrogen peroxide. It has been found that they also react with hydrogen peroxide with the production of carbon dioxide. The mechanism of the reaction can be explained as follows.

When salts of tungstic acid and molybdic acid are allowed to react with *ortho*-dihydroxy compounds, they oxidise the hydroxy compounds to

the corresponding quinones forming a complex. When hydrogen peroxide is added, the reduced salts are oxidised and the complex is dissociated. They then react with hydrogen peroxide forming per-salts which further oxidise the quinones with the production of carbon dioxide.

About the mechanism of peroxidase action, majority of opinions favour the formation of an active enzyme-substrate complex between the peroxidase and hydrogen peroxide (Willstätter and Weber, *Annalen*, 1926, 449, 156) and the view that the reducing substrate also combines with the enzyme has not hitherto been accepted (Haldane, "Enzymes," 1930 Ed.). Willstätter and Weber found that excess of hydrogen peroxide decreases the activity of peroxidase and ultimately inhibits the reaction. This inactivation may be combated either by increasing the concentration of reducing substrate or by decreasing the concentration of hydrogen peroxide by means of catalase. To explain this phenomenon they suggested that the peroxidase reacts with hydrogen peroxide forming two additive compounds corresponding to the formulae $\text{HO} - \text{OH}$ and $\text{H}_2\text{O} = \text{O}$ for hydrogen peroxide. At low concentration of hydrogen peroxide it combines with the peroxidase in the form $\text{H}_2\text{O} = \text{O}$ to give a compound which is catalytically active and in high concentration it combines as $\text{HO} - \text{OH}$ to give a compound which is relatively inactive and requires a high concentration of reducing substrate for its decomposition.

As the above explanation is unsatisfactory in explaining all the observed facts, recently a theory has been put forward by Mann (*Biochem. J.*, 1931, 25, 918) and by Woolf (*ibid.*, 1931, 25, 342) in which they have put forward the hypothesis that all the substrates must be combined at the enzyme before catalysis can take place. Both the reducing substrate and hydrogen peroxide combine at their respective groups which are moderately specific. But when hydrogen peroxide is in excess, it combines with the nonspecific group keeping the reducing substrate away and hence causing inhibition. This inhibition may be combated either by increasing the concentration of reducing substrate or by destroying the H_2O_2 by means of catalase as shown by Willstätter and Weber (*loc. cit.*). Similar conclusion has been drawn by Balls and Hale (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1934, 107, 787) from a study of the inhibition and specificity of peroxidase.

Shibata (*Acta Phytochim Japan*, 1929, 4, 373) from a study of the complex metal salts, has deduced the following theory of the mechanism of action of oxidases, peroxidases and catalases. According to him the oxidase combines loosely with H_2O in which process, part of its energy is transferred to H_2O and activate it to $\text{H}(\cdot) - \text{H}$. The OH radical dehydrogenates the substrate molecule and H combines with atmospheric oxygen

or with any other hydrogen acceptor. The peroxidase combines with hydrogen peroxide and similarly activates it to HO - OH. The HO radical dehydrogenates the substrate molecules. In a like manner, catalase activates H_2O_2 simultaneously to H - O - O - H and HO - OH. By mutual hydrogenation and dehydrogenation of these two activated forms, decomposition of hydrogen peroxide takes place. Thus the mechanism of the action of these enzymes is virtually the same. He showed that the mechanism of the activation of hydrogen peroxide by complex metal salts and by natural peroxidases was identical, since mutual interference occurs in solutions containing the complex metal salt together with the natural enzyme.

Now the study of the behaviour of peroxidases and tungstic acid, molybdic acid, vanadic acid with different substrates shows that the mechanism of reaction is not the same in both cases. Should the peroxidase activity be due to its combination with hydrogen peroxide alone as is the case with sols, there would not be such a marked difference as given in sections (B) and (C), when there is an increase in the concentration of reducing substrate and hydrogen peroxide, the products of reaction being the same in both cases. The difference may be due to the adsorption of both reducing substrate and hydrogen peroxide in the case of peroxidase as has been assumed by Mann (*loc. cit.*).

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CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
DACCA UNIVERSITY.

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